

IPBES values assessment

Literature review for the philosophies of good living

Results of the analysis

Team

Coding and analysis: Simone Athayde (Ch2), Elena Lazos (Ch4), Lelani Mannetti (Ch5), Sofia Monroy (Ch1), Ranjini Murali (Ch2), Tuyeni Mwampamba (Ch3), Sara Nelson (Ch4), Agnes Pawlowska-Mainville (Ch4), Luciana Porter-Bolland (Ch6), Ricardo Rozzi (Ch5), Alejandra Tauro (CA), Eglee Zent (Ch2)

Other coders: Rachelle K. Gould (Ch2), Javier Mejía (CA)

Other collaborators: Gabriel Nemogá (Ch3), Mariaelena Huambachano (Ch3), Sebastián Ballestas (CA)

TSU Support: Mariana Cantú, David González, Gabriela Arroyo, Victoria Contreras

General information

General description of the reviewed papers

The Philosophies of Good Living literature review comprised 235 academic papers and books, out of which 204 were available in a language that allowed experts to code them. Figure (1) shows the languages in which these 204 papers were retrieved, most of which (159) were in English. Figure (2) shows the types of documents that were coded. Coders provided this information for 150 documents, and during the analysis phase, information was completed for 54 more. The range of years of publication of the documents is shown in Figure (3). This range goes from 1981 to 2021, being 2018 the year with the most publications.

Figure 1. Language of the documents. Most of the papers reviewed (159 = 77.9%) were publications in English. Papers in Spanish, Portuguese and French were also included in the review.

Figure 2. Types of documents reviewed. 90 papers (44.1%) reported results of fieldwork, and in consequence they were considered as empirical documents. Perspective papers (57 papers) talked about Good Living Philosophies in current contexts at multiple scales and potential evolution of those contexts considering the application of these philosophies. Review/Analysis papers (50 papers) considered multiple sources of information, to present the state of the art of a topic involving Good Living Philosophies, or to describe multiple conditions of a selected theme, respectively. Philosophy papers analysed and explained the Good Living Philosophies (6 papers) and 1 paper presented the memoirs of the author, an Aboriginal woman, and her view on the philosophy presented in her paper.

Figure 3. Years of publication of reviewed papers.

Cultural, local, indigenous groups and communities

Throughout the 204 coded papers, 102 different cultural, local and indigenous groups and communities are mentioned. Figure 4 presents the names of the mentioned groups.

Figure 4. Cultural, indigenous, and local communities and groups present in the papers reviewed. Sizes of the names are proportional to the amount of times each of these groups or communities appeared in the literature reviewed.

Geographical location of the papers

Most of the reviewed papers (122) focused their research within a single country. Papers discussing international regions such as Latin America or Sub-saharan Africa, or proposing analysis at the global scale were 35. Papers that compared or applied studies in two countries were 19 (13 of these, were based in both Ecuador and Bolivia at the same time), and documents covering more than 2 countries were 9. Two papers talked about Ecuador and expanded their conclusions to South America, and finally, for 17 papers this information was not specified. Figure 5 shows the frequency of papers based in different countries around the world, without making distinctions between studies based in a single country or in more than one. The map does not consider documents basing their research on regions or at the global scale.

Figure 5. Geographical location of the studies reviewed for the Philosophies of Good Living literature review.

Overview of ilk values

Philosophies of good living

In the literature reviewed, diverse values and principles associated with philosophies of good living were identified, the most common being *harmony* (47 references), *reciprocity* (40 references), *solidarity* (28 references), *community* (26 references) and *respect* (26 references; Figure 6). In general, when grouping keywords used to describe the values, the most referred to concepts included *relationality* (Figure 7). In the reviewed papers we identified 74 indigenous philosophies related to the notion of good-living, they shared a lot of commonalities and values despite being from very different parts of the world (Figure 5). Another 21 local philosophies were identified (Figure 8). These philosophies offer alternatives to the main development paradigm, including changes in the economic capitalist system and on how wealth can be interpreted and looked for [35 references]; for example, focusing on happiness rather than on material accumulation. Also these philosophies are seen as a way to decolonize knowledge and offer different educational models. Non indigenous philosophies emerge from local frameworks and communities, but also from academics, activists and citizens, for example: eco-feminism, deep ecology, moral wealth, multidimensional well-being, slow cities, satoumi and satoyama. Yet more multiple values are usually highlighted within these philosophies or frameworks [21 references], while relational values tend to prevail in indigenous philosophies.

Figure 6. The most frequently used key terms to describe the values and principles associated with the good living philosophies in the papers reviewed. Exact words used by coders are displayed, and only terms used 3 or more times are depicted. Papers reviewed overlap between categories and contained multiple key terms.

Figure 7. The most common key concepts used to describe the values and principles associated with the good living philosophies in the papers reviewed. Words are grouped according to general meaning (for example relationality = all keywords indicating connection). Depicted here are the top 10 most common key concepts

The most iconic characteristic of these philosophies through the reviewed papers is the harmonious and respectful human and nature relations to achieve a good life [40 references]. Life is usually seen as a web of relations, which are reciprocal and often non utilitarian. In this web, all life and biodiversity has the right to exist and they represent a heritage to current and future generations, and in response there is duty to care for life. Other important characteristics of these good living philosophies that stand out are: meaningful human-human relationships [27 references], holism [23 references], collective well-being [21 references], the promotion of biocultural diversity [17 references], non-duality between humans and nature [14 references], and the importance of the cycles of life [8 references], among others.

challenges in specific places and merge with non-indigenous discourses. However, some authors argue that these umbrella concepts have lost their meaning in their translations and sometimes the concepts have been oversimplified and tend to romanticize indigenous and local people [408; 94].

In some communities, regions and countries, these philosophies have been incorporated into policy by different mechanisms, as a way to articulate their values in political agendas [14 references]. For example, Bhutan's gross national happiness; the Buen Vivir paradigm and the Rights of Nature or "Pachamama" in the constitutions of Ecuador and Bolivia; the "Planes de Vida" in Colombia; or the Yasuni ITT Initiative to keep oil underground, among others. However, some critics have pointed out the use of good living philosophies by elites and political actors for their own interests or in contradiction with the core values [11 references], for example the use of neo-extractivism forms in Latin America, or Ubuntu by political actors just to gain popular acceptance.

Importantly, it is the dependence and interconnectedness these philosophies evince with nature in non-material forms, a spiritual connection to places [14 references]; for example the concept of "Wáman Lware" from the Kamëntšá in Colombia, which means "an intimate place, which allows to create memory of a place through knowledge-memory-experience" [387]. Some of these philosophies also enhance the process of self-determination, local autonomy and identity [9 references].

Links with cross-cutting themes

Regarding **economy**, in the Ayni philosophy for example, there is an obligation to share excess production with the community to be redistributed among vulnerable people, a change to a solidary economy and equity. Also some philosophies favour austerity over consumer culture, with attention to social relationships over attention to making money.

Regarding **agriculture**, agroecology is highlighted as a way to reconcile production, land and nature [127]. In practice, indigenous peasant movements have made possible the inclusion of the concept of food sovereignty associated with the buen vivir philosophy in the constitution of Ecuador [439].

In the case of **infrastructure**, the Kalamboan philosophy is marked by improvements in infrastructure, tidiness and cleanliness of the built and natural environments and institutionalised community organising. Kalamboan literally means growth, flourishing, or an unfolding of fertile potential [74].

Relevance for **gender**: some papers link indigenous philosophies like the Buen Vivir with certain occidental traditions which have challenged cultural basis of dominant modernity, for example Feminism [575, 60]. In relation with the collective well-being "Aggregating the many proposals for communal life, such as those of the Zapatistas or the Kurds, as well as a multiplicity of feminist movements" [396]. The Nahuatl philosophy from Mexico of Kualli Nemilistli is based on love which is intended to not depend on the discipline system and the masculine prerogatives [462]. In some indigenous groups the notion of good living by women has been associated with personal autonomy and more power, for example the Maasai [599]. Ubuntu is used along with sorority as an epistemological path to inspire women's alliances to fight for equal rights and freedom, and against racism, power imbalances, prejudice and misogyny against Afro-descendant women and LGBT groups [183].

Regarding **ecoliteracy or knowledge** about nature, these philosophies place a high emphasis in the a traditional wisdom and how the value system reinforces these knowledge as a form of constant dialogue with nature, "knowledge about life" [107; 24; 155]

Topic 1: Human-nature relationships, biocultural diversity and worldviews

Figure 9. Worldviews represented in the literature review, with value types under each worldview. Multiple refers to multiple different values. The y-axis provides the number of papers reviewed.

Figure 10. Emergent themes under worldviews

In this section all papers marked 2 and 3 under relevance for human-nature relationships were reviewed. In total, 100 papers were reviewed, 63 papers marked as 3 (very relevant) and 37 papers marked as 2 (moderately relevant). Under human-nature relationships there were two sub-sections, which were “Worldviews” and “Bio-cultural diversity”. 12 papers were reviewed under bio-cultural diversity, and 93 papers under worldviews. Some papers were relevant for both bio-cultural diversity and worldviews. The themes for worldviews are first presented, followed by themes for bio-cultural diversity. Finally, papers relevant for the cross-sectional themes are discussed, followed by a brief overview of the emergent gaps from the papers reviewed.

Worldviews: Emergent themes related to worldviews are provided below

1. **Pluricentric worldviews (59 papers):** Majority of the papers reflected Pluricentric worldviews (63%), followed by Anthropocentric (10.8%), and Biocentric (5.4%) (Figure 9). Pluricentric worldviews focus on the relationships between human-and-nature, and there is no separation between humans and nature. For example a quote from paper ID 303, captures this well “Our relationship with our mother the earth, the water, with all of the different plants, medicine, the herbs, the animals, the birds, all the four legged being[s]. Everything we encounter in our lives there is a relationship that we are always reminded of and are mindful about. We see ourselves belonging to the entire existence of our world; we are not separated from anything. Wahkohtowin talks about embodying that entire holistic idea of how we exist”.

4 of the 10 papers that were classified as Anthropocentric, reflected a “Weak Anthropocentric” worldview. The classification of these worldviews into these categories reflect the positionality of the authors describing the worldviews, and the aspects that they chose to focus on. For example, 6 of the 10 papers coded as Anthropocentric referred to the African concept of Ubuntu i.e. “I am a person through others”. In total though, there were 10 papers that referred to Ubuntu, but 4 of these papers discussed Ubuntu as a Pluricentric worldview. In the papers coded as anthropocentric, the authors chose to focus on the human-human relationships, and the community only referred to people. Whereas the papers that categorized Ubuntu as Pluricentric, focused on human-nature interconnectedness and broadened the definition of community to include nature, for eg “the land is me”.

2. **Relational values (46):** Relational values were the most prevalent under each worldview with relational values representing 64% (38 out of 59 papers) of the values under Pluricentric worldview, 60% (3 out of 5 papers) under Biocentric, and 50% (5 out of 10 papers) under Anthropocentric worldviews. See figure 9 for the complete distribution of value types under each worldview. The relational values that were most commonly referred to were Reciprocity (between people and people, people and nature, people and the spirit world), Care, Love, Harmony (between people and people, people and nature), Respect (for nature, people, elders), kinship, solidarity, and the idea of balance. In this context, these values extended beyond human relationship to include the natural and spirit world.
3. **Community values (30):** There was a strong emphasis on community and social values, over the self, which emphasized solidarity and collective well-being. The community includes people and nature and the unity-oneness of humanity and nature.

4. **Interconnectedness (34):** Buen vivir and allied concepts recognize the idea of interconnectedness, i.e., human well-being is dependant on the welfare of the earth as well as the spiritual world and ancestors, and intergenerational connectedness.
5. **Cultural identity (10):** Cultural identity is important in Indigenous worldviews
6. **Rituals (3):** The expressions of these values and worldviews are embedded in rituals and practices which include offerings and gifts to nature.
7. **Knowledge systems (:** Indigenous worldviews are also shaped by traditional knowledge systems which are place-based and are transferred intergenerationally. Indigenous scholars produce knowledge according to indigenous worldviews.
8. **Alternative to development (42):** Buen vivir and allied concepts offer an alternative to western development based on worldviews embedded in relational values such as care, reciprocity, harmony and the community as opposed to worldviews embedded in instrumental values. They encompass different forms of knowledge and remove the human-nature dualism. They can provide an opportunity to build a different society sustained in the coexistence of human beings in their diversity and in harmony with nature, based on recognition of the diverse cultural values existing in each country and worldwide. Paper ID no 382 describes this as "there is no reason to 'develop' anywhere, the point is rather to preserve (or regain) that sort of state of harmonious living of all peoples and living beings."
9. **Decolonization (26):** Buen vivir and indigenous worldviews were used for decolonizing ideas and ways of living, doing, and knowing. Paper ID 570 expresses, "it tries to recover and understand the ancestral knowledge and to recover the indigenous-original wisdom of millenary cultures that establish the "sacred way". This search does not mean, under any logic, to go back to the past, but to re-gain the principles and values that have no time or space." These worldviews were applied to decolonize ideas of health (which often referred to the concept of one health, i.e health of the people and nature are interlinked, as is mental and physical health), peace building and conflict resolution, human rights framework, justice, medicine, education, governance, farming, and communication theory.
10. **Justice (28):** Indigenous worldviews were used to conceptualize ideas of social and ecological justice grounded in indigenous epistemology and ontological foundations. This includes recognizing mutually beneficial relationships with the living and non-living world, and ancestors. Justice is recognized in terms of collective rights and collective justice. Redistributive justice, described as social justice through redistribution and holistic development is also discussed.
11. There are also different dimensions of justice which expands to include **Rights Of Nature (9)**, which recognizes that nature has rights, and **Rights To Nature (4)**, which recognizes that people have rights to nature such as the right to clean air and water. This can promote engagement and ethical conduct, which includes nature, and can lead to just and sustainable outcomes.
12. **Local resource management (4):** Indigenous worldviews are reflected in local management of natural resources according to traditional systems. They are often democratic, and have collective

ownership and management. They are also considered more sustainable and resilient as they are based on values such as reciprocity, harmony, care, and balance.

13. **Exclusion from global agenda (1):** However, Indigenous worldviews are excluded from current conceptualizations of development and the global agenda like the SDG, and this can lead to depression and feelings of non-relevance among indigenous people.
14. **Leadership (2):** Leadership that reflects indigenous worldviews, values, and aspirations in decision-making and institutional contexts is essential for indigenous well-being.
15. **Decision-making (17):** Incorporation and recognition of indigenous worldviews in decision-making is important for their self-determination and autonomy. Indigenous cosmologies and traditional values may be strengthened through their integration into modern policies and institutions. For example, In 2007, Ecuador was the first country in the world to reserve an area of 7500 km² as an Intangible area, reserved for the rights to self-determination of uncontacted people Tagaeri Taromenane.
16. **Incorrect incorporation in decision making (7):** However, the way it is incorporated is important. While incorporation into the constitutions of Bolivia and Ecuador are used as good examples, there are tensions between the practiced concept of *Beun vivir* (more pluricentric) and those adopted by the constitutions of Ecuador and Bolivia where it almost translates into a different form of extraction of natural resources (more anthropocentric). In the State's conceptualization, it is linked to neoextractive, and the good life is linked to urbanization, future city and coexists with oil-extraction
17. **Critique (1):** *Buen vivir* as it essentializes women and their role and connection to nature
18. **Emerging political movement (1):** *Buen vivir* is considered an emerging political movement that challenges the current system.

Biocultural Diversity Themes

Under biocultural diversity all the emergent themes were related to food production systems.

1. Traditional food systems recognize the interdependence of biodiversity and food, and communities and biodiversity have coadapted in these systems (8)
2. Indigenous food systems and practices can empower communities, and lead to food security and food sovereignty (8)
3. Indigenous food systems are built on the principle of reciprocity, which encourages sustainable living (2)
4. Indigenous food systems and practices promote healthy ecosystems (4)
5. Rights to produce food (1)

Links with cross-cutting themes

Regarding **economy**, the articles mentioned under the theme Alternative Development in the linked excel sheet fall under this category. The papers discuss alternative systems of production and

consumptions, markets, and development models based on relational values of reciprocity, harmony, care, etc.

Regarding **agriculture**, all the articles under bioculture diversity refer to agro-ecological systems, which are relevant for this theme. They discuss indigenous management systems, biocultural diversity of food production systems, food security, and sovereignty, and the right to produce food. La campesina, a South American food movement, and Satoyama, traditional agricultural production in Japan are also discussed.

Relevance for **gender**: (387) – describes the cosmovision of the Kanëtsa and concepts of justice, self-determination, and autonomy and how it links to gender. (30) – describes food systems and markets managed by women; (582) discuss gender equity. Connect women with the power of mother earth, and stories are transmitted through women and their bodies understand the circle of life.

(103) is a Environmental feminist critique of the Buen Vivir concept and approach to climate justice. “Certain Latin American feminists are questioning this proposed “civilizational shift.” Pointing to the dangers of idealizing and essentializing traditional communities. buen vivir is a value system specifying ethical and spiritual codes of conduct in relation to the greater social and natural environment / Women/we had to [separate ourselves from nature] in order to show that being a woman is a cultural construct, that we are not a continuity of nature / woman. Especially troubling for feminists is the nature relation as anthropomorphized in notions of Mother Earth and the Pachamama. Such notions serve to reinforce women’s assigned role as caregiver by essentializing it and by accusing...Women who choose to practice family planning of violating tradition / denies rights of reproductive right”

Relevance for **Education**: Education is mostly discussed in the context of using Buen Vivir and allied concepts to decolonize education (469 and 417). There is focus on community engagement and the values that are taught to children (465)

Topic 2: Languages

A total of 34 articles were analysed for the Languages topic, including all papers rated 2 and 3 by the coders. The most important findings from this analysis are summarized in the chart and on the set of 12 main messages, summarized below:

Figure 11. Main emerging ideas connected to Topic 2: Languages, for the Philosophies of Good Living case-study analysis.

1. Despite the existence of many commonalities among IPLCs, regarding concepts connected to Philosophies of Good Living, there **are also specificities and linguistic expressions and distinctions that need to be recognized**. As Heikkilä (2016/#221) points out regarding Sámi's conceptualization of "good life", denoted as "buorre eallin", **specific concepts and values expressed in Indigenous languages and dialects need to be examined considering the biocultural context in which the language evolved and it is used**. These distinctions are recognized/ mentioned in 15 papers, or 44% of the articles analysed. One interesting comment connected to this message, is that we could refer to Buen Vivir as "Buenos Viveres", as "an opportunity to build a society that is based on the coexistence of the human being in diversity and harmony with nature, based on the diverse cultural values that exist in each country and in the world" (Constanzo 2016/#112).
2. Many **linguistic expressions used by IPLCs denote ethical or moral principles of how to live (well)**. Thus, **language can be considered a "repository" or a "place" where core ethical principles and values are stored**. This is true for many Indigenous peoples referred to in the analysed articles, **as well as religions**, such as **Taoism**. Some examples of these guiding principles are found among the: Anishinaabek; Hawai'ian groups; Maya, Quechua, Aymara, Kicha, Maori, Yawuru, Bemba, Mbyá guarani; Inuit; and Haudenosaunee. Half or 50% of the analysed articles bring this perspective, directly or indirectly. For instance, African moral systems tend to respond to the dignity of human beings by emphasizing duties instead of rights (Akinola and Uzodike 2017/#12). Among the Anishinaabek, the value of "respect for the spirit in all things is rooted in Indigenous legal orders",

denoted by the expression "mino-mnaamodzawin" (McGregor 2018/#359). The Haudenosaunee tradition configured the first treaty in North America, the **Two Row Wampum**, which is based on the principle of sharing land and knowledge (Sheridan 2014/#517).

3. The idea that **all life or creation is interconnected and interdependent, existing as kin, was present in 10 (29.41%) articles** analysed for the languages topic. This denotes a strong relational worldview and correspondent relational values such as reciprocity, interdependence and intergenerational connectedness (Mohatt et al. 2011; Ullrich 2019 / #569). These values are being articulated in postcolonial educational programs. Contrasting with Western values and educational systems: Western: The land is mine. African/Zambian/Bemba people: The Land is me (Spencer 2018/ #534).
4. Another relevant message which emerged from the analyses is the recommendation that **postcolonial educational policies must include ILK and IPLCs values**, supported by 9 papers (26.47%). These articles highlighted the oppressive aspect of Western-based education developed in postcolonial countries, and the need to decolonize educational systems to include diverse knowledge systems, values, and languages.
5. The **right to a "good life"** was also mentioned in some articles, especially contrasting to the right to "development" (7 articles, 20.59%). In this topic, special emphasis was given to the right to a healthy environment present in many Constitutions, and what would that entail from an ILK/IPLC perspective.
6. **The mis-appropriation or manipulation of Buen Vivir and related concepts** by politicians and elites was also detected in 4 of the articles analysed (11.76%). This idea is not directly tied to languages, and probably was also expressed/found in other relevant topics. Of special interest is Mayta (2017)/paper #94, already mentioned by Eglee, which brings a very critical view of Buen Vivir as a concept manufactured by social groups for political reasons in Bolivia, including supporting child labor.
7. The fact that **designations and management of landscapes are strongly attached to place-based identities** was also highlighted in 4 articles or 11.76%. This is connected to topic 1, and could be potentially merged / combined with the need to consider specific biocultural contexts in which languages, concepts and cultures co-evolved. There is a specific example of Satoyama in Japan that illustrates this idea well.
8. **The importance of language rights and specific policies toward languages** was present in 3 articles (8.82%). For example, Heikkilä (2016/#221) highlights the fact that even if there are provisions recognizing the use of Sami language in the Finish Constitution, this is not enough to promote its continuity outside community efforts. The application of the Sámi Language Act is restricted to the Sámi Homeland. Moreover, the Act is interpreted narrowly such that it does not impose an explicit duty on government authorities to provide such services. This is also connected with the cross-cutting topic of Ecoliteracy. In Australia, of the 250 languages spoken pre-invasion, just 60 remain as a living language (Korff, 2014). Moreover, in 2008, just 62% of Aboriginal adults reported identifying with a clan, language, or tribal group (Korff, 2014). Neocolonialism continues to impose western knowledge and values over local languages, knowledge systems and values (Härtel 2015/

215). The marginalization/ isolation of languages by national policies exacerbates the loss of ecoliteracy and contributes to the erosion of knowledge and values connected to the homelands where these languages co-evolved since times immemorial.

9. One specific topic that emerged from this analysis (2 articles, 5.88%) is the importance of promoting **children's formal and informal education in their native languages and considering values** held by IPLCs. This is connected with concepts such as intergenerational and epistemic justice.
10. Articles also presented interesting **conceptualisations of health held by IPLCs**, which could be incorporated in health-related policies and/or human-environmental health policies / frameworks (such as the ONE health concept). Agner et al. (2020 / #9) for Hawai'i; Pichasaca (2020 / # 450).
11. An interesting proposition emerging from 2 articles (5.88%) was that **countering the degradation of valued landscapes requires fundamental changes in social systems**, including people in urban centers, and not only conserving IPLCs territories and protected areas. Special mention to Satoyama landscapes in Japan (Iwata et al. 2011 / # 251).
12. Finally, 2 articles (5.88%) presented the attempt of **developing Indigenous-based indicators of well-being**, which could be integrated in policies directed to IPLCs and beyond (Yap and Yu 2016 # 609).
13. A last message, present in only one paper, but relevant for **how to incorporate IPLCs values/ILK into instrumental values and decisions**, is the use of Maori principles to run their business/economies. According to Härtel (2015 / #215), the **Maori view business as having the goal of creating well-being** (mauri ora), which includes "healing and sustaining life". Management decisions are assessed according to Maori values.

Topic 3: Diversity of knowledge for decision-making, including valuation methods

No analysis was performed for this topic as part of this report, but rather, relevant information coded under it was analysed and included in chapter 3.

Topic 4: Self-determination, juridical pluralism, IPLCs rights and institutions and knowledge for decision-making

The reflection on this global topic is divided in three broad sections: (1) raw numerical aspects, (2) main themes that derive from the 107 coded publications, and (3) critical pertinent concerns.

Numbers

Out of 204 coded papers, 107 (52.45%) of them were considered within a value scale of importance as 3 (59) or 2 (48). Therefore, self-determination, juridical pluralism, rights, institutions and knowledge for decision making among ILP are overall, issues pondered as meaningful for more than half of the recent literature reviewed. Albeit, there are many obstacles that allow the legal and juridical corpus of national and international documents that guarantee the rights of ILP as well as *nature*, the trends to apply them observe convoluted paths. In that sense a warning to consider the following main themes is advised.

A set of 13 prevalent and relevant themes were globally identified as listed below.

The numbers in brackets refer to the number of publications that support the specific theme associated to the virtues or critics dynamized by Buen Vivir (BV) or Vivir Bien (VB):

1. The claim that BV constitutes an alternative to development, being its central value the solidarity that potentially permeated all economic institutions to generate a different system [39]. Among the issues worth to mention in this theme are the following, specif Andean mechanism of interchange such as minga, ofrendas, trueque [200, 461], IPLC use BV as policial agenda even other groups such as Amazonian ones have adopted for that [363], food sovereignty in Ecuador shaped by IP org [439], building utopias local economies/markets [4], woman in control of barter market huge amounts of food products [30], touches probably all topics good paper [60].
2. Considering BV as a trigger to decolonization, as well as the articulation of social and ecological justice which leads to the building of a more just society [44]. The sub themes relevant in this group of publications include: gender mangement and political subject [247], ecological justice from IP perspective [359], CBD and BV [594], different ways to meassure wellbeing [609]/comparison btw BV and declaration of hman rights [22], butan wellbeingindex [45], central to understand and examples of decolonization and law [137], BV cholo in novel [207].
3. The Capacity of BV as a main strategy to reach a civilizatory change, emphasizing pluriversality as an alternative scenario to "progress" or "development" [51]. This comprehensive theme include issues as the listed here: legal right of pachamama [240], gender, importance of women as political subjects [247, 249], importance of interface of spiritual/political networks of strategies [312], Andean IP intellectuals emphasize pol eco, Amazonians underlight pol-ecol ones [461], written by IP [517], critique to the modernist values underlying sustainability as international conservation agenda [573, 574], epistemic justice [594]/ women and alternative economies [30], harmony as a legal resistance concept [40], communication theory [86], agroecology and food security based on BV values and 3 South American constitutions, Bol, Ec, Vzla [598].
4. *Ubuntu* or alternative similar dynamics to BV worldwide not just in South America [11]. Worth to mention are these issues: gender [black female, Brazil 183], essential to understand ubuntu and

- justice overall not exclusively nature [217], compares BV, ubuntu, and gross national happiness [573], comparison ubuntu and teko pora Guarani [417], land is me African view [534],
5. Love-based framework of practice, as an explicit central value of BV dynamics [5]. A shift of paradigm that has an emotional backbone was emphasized on these subthemes: Love explicitly articulated in feminist participatory action research (FPAR) but justified as a main goal of BV (to love and be loved) [182], care and love associated to all creation not just humans [359], more important to teach what to love that knowledge per se [465, ubuntu], kin love and kindness [477].
 6. Several observations associated with critical views that underscore the internal contradictions of discourse and praxis of BV in the community, society or ethnic groups dynamics [21]. Including the role of IP as political leaders. Structural and specific contradictions of BV: use of neoliberal views and politics implemented, notion of capital not even questioned [46], lack of a critical view that underlies no correlation of practices to a discourse that is turning hegemonic; major tension in communal social organization, BV, legal and economic dynamics [325], deep contradiction between BV and Bolivian economic dynamics, idyllic representation of IP communities [35], main analysis just legal [149], contradictions BV, class and eco [309], critique urbanization process of rural Ecuador framed on BV favoring the powerful elite as usual [513],
 7. Critical perspectives that describe how BV is used to justify a project or plan (at local, regional, national and even international scales) which are rather, very well articulated to accumulation/development system or as a political agenda from IPLC [30]. Each publication deals with specific cases and criticisms: immense contradictions to implement the BV notion at national and international levels [46], important to highlight the use of the BV to accommodate the status quo, in this case gov [111], points structural complexity of Nature laws in Ecuador to support neoliberal system [240], contradictions of ecology-economy en Ecuador legal system [311], use and adoption of BV by the IPLC assoc in their pol agendas [363]/ permanent negotiation of the values of BV and the implementation of economic projects in Bolivia [35], progress concept revisited and criticized [45], tensions constitution, gov, BV[310], survey of BV perception of dif actors in Ecuador and its legal status [349], comparison Russia-Bolivia amply manipulative pol discourses [383], legitimizing a elite power discourse justified in BV [513].
 8. The description and analysis of diverse typologies of BV highlighting the plurality of the notion in terms of origin (indigenous, academia, government, NGOs, communities, regions, etc.) that oftentimes carry different meanings and trigger diverse processes [6]. Very interesting desgloses of origins and developments of BV: 1) 'indigenous' , 2) poststructuralist, 3) socialist [112], provides a contrast of theoretical concepts used by academia and the IP association of Trapecio amazonico that adopted the BV notion for their political agenda [380], mentions four sources in the construction of BV paradigm [60]/ three BV: people, gov, scientists [126], quote two typologies of the lit [349].
 9. Alternative local philosophies alike to BV that are even linguistically encoded elsewhere not in South America [20], specifically: Guatemala [144], North America [152], Amazon [163], China [220], Finland [221], Japan [251], Canada [303], Navajo/Dine [318], Anishinaabek, Canada [359], New Guinea, Fiji [477], Anishinaabeg [517], compares BV, ubuntu, and gross nat happiness [573], Yawuru, Australia [609], /Hawai'i [9], Maori rugby team [209], small scale fishers all over the world and dif values in def of BV [255], mentions many without developing them [333], Satomi Japan [373], spiritual bonds Russia [384], New Zealand Maori Mana Kaitiakitanga [610].
 10. Pronouncing BV as a potential international eco-bio-cultural governance system [15]. One of the most relevant examples is Yasuni, in the Ecuadorian Amazon which raises questions of the

immaturity of the international commitment to international ecological policies platform which is now known, as the Yasunization [3], that is, the lack of support of international community to pay for Yasuni, Ecuador and opening to oil drill [307,126, 308]/ and a program to renew values material and spiritual through education [104]. Also relevant are the issues of how the same constitution grants laws to extractivism, humans and nature rights, inherent structural/legal contradictions [307, 126], dif nature as a legal subject [149].

11. Explicit request to eliminate separation between human-nature, stressing that everything is interconnected, interdependent, and interrelated [18].
12. Controversies and contradictions raised of legal systems internal/ancestral to ILP vs the hegemonic one [19]. Worth to mention here are the comuna and historical rights over territories and BV [19], in a negative way autonomy of communities to force labor on children and weaker members of society based on BV legal status [94],
14. Explicit relevance of ontological, political, sacred discourses associated to the human and other-than-human entities/persons with legal or prominent status, that is, the open inclusion of non-human entities as equals in rights [8]

Given the potential legal perspectives generated by BV or VB paradigm, two macro critical perspectives developed by several publications are of the uppermost consequences:

1. The history of how the term BV was coined.
2. The potential use of BV to justify human rights abuses

In the first case, two papers Bold [63] and Chambi [94] openly describe how the concept of Vivir Bien was developed in a workshop sponsored by GTZ in 2001 ascribed to be an indigenous concept of development. Rather some intellectuals (Simon Yampara, Javier Medina, Dominique Temple, Jacqueline Michaux) coined in Spanish the term BV or VB and urged their translation in different Aeriandian languages. BV quickly gained international success, representing the contribution of Andean people to an alternative world order. However, it fetishizes and reifies indigenous identities, associated with a static idyllic past, denying the ILP their contemporary choices. BV as National Plans in settings non prone to grant equal rights to IP could actually denigrate and ultimately harm the autonomy and rights of IP.

Given than BV was elevated to a official juridical constitutional status in at least two countries, Bolivia and Ecuador, being guiding principle for basically all state policies, it is important to warn of its use in a rank of positive and constructive values as well as its abuse an use to justify human rights as highlighted by Chambi [94]. BV allegedly substantiated laws passed by the Bolivian government that support cruel cases of child labor realities. This questioning comes from inside the value of VB even, from Bolivian indigenous scholars, politicians and intellectuals (mostly Aymara). The literature provides clear examples that denies the harmony, equilibrium, solidarity and reciprocity values of VB among indgenous communities (children labor, sexual abuses, etc)

Paradigm shift, legal and ontological [137]

Real legal analysis [149]

It may also be helpful to mention some of the literature reviewed that is not relevant for this particular topic 4: 6, 77, 110, 324 [little], 465, 59, 62, [more to education topic], 79 [more communication theory not that relevant], 86 [more on communication theory of change], 128 [no mention of nature, BV or NCP], 209 [more related to identity and belonging self esteem of Maori rugby team that NCP or BV per se], 242 [more related to economic development and potential strategies of ILP no BV or NCP mentioned or legal aspects], 255 [lack of legal system and dif def of BV not Andean proposal, 417 [more relevant for education], 450 [notion of health of cañari, inclusive comprehensive of BV but not for topic 4], more education but in Africa ubuntu and land [534], more endo-education topic in an Amazonian community feeding the BV [538].

Topic 5: Protecting land, territories and places

A total of 55 papers were examined to discuss the link between the philosophy of good living and territorial rights concerning people who identify as Indigenous and who enunciate their views and interests to emphasize 'local ways of knowing' and 'different local histories', especially when tied to sovereignty (13 papers).

Social and environmental governance that promotes resurgence of culture and territoriality is gaining popularity as a governance principle. In Bolivia, Ecuador, and Peru, the concept of 'buen vivir' has been institutionalized and indigenous values such as equilibrium, harmony, and complementarity with Mother Earth and the community have been embedded in diverse socio-environmental policies (Chambi 2017; Merino 2016; Giovanni 2012). As a response to values associated with capitalism, acculturation, and growth of resource-development industries, the cultural philosophies represent an additional and highly contrasted value to take into account when making land and resource-based decisions and for supporting IPCL territoriality. Literature shows that the philosophies can serve as legal and ethical mechanisms, enabling States and policy makers to inform decision-making and pursue claims to sovereignty. For example, among the Anishinaabeg (Indigenous people) in Canada, land is a source of 'good life [mino-bimaadiziwin]' and Anishinaabeg Elders relied on the term of maintaining a good life to strengthen their responsibility coexistence with the land through own cultural governance and an Indigenous-led World Heritage Site called Pimachiowin Aki.

To illustrate, Ecuador and Bolivia both relied on the philosophes as constitutional reforms for responding to climate change. In 2008, Ecuador became the first country in the world to recognize the Rights of Nature in its Constitution, in order to face climate change and to restore the ecological footprint (Collado-Ruano, J; Madronero-Morillo, M; Alvarez-Gonzalez, F 2019). In China, villagers' collective identity and reinvented clan system was restored when villages united to resist land deprivation and rural identity (Xe et al 2014). The philosophy was used not only to provide a more equitable approach to the resources and a great decision-making power to marginalized groups, but in many cases, they were used as counter-hegemonic strategies for decolonization and a mechanism for protection of cultural landscapes (Kayira J.2015). While these local cosmovisions are often poorly understood and not respected by dominant elites and legal functionaries of the state, they serve to ensure a people's well-being on the lands they call 'home'. (Hoekema, A 2017).

The philosophies across literature point to the view that humans are a part of nature and directly affected by it, inherently creates a certain level of responsibility towards each other and future generations. However, the practical application of these cultural philosophies are not without their challenges. First World neoliberal countries, totalitarian governments, corporate businesses, and enterprises abroad are continuing the destruction of IPLC lands, territories, sacred places, and intangible and natural resources. A large component is due to free- trade regimes as well as the non-binding nature of the International Labor Organization's Convention 169 (ILO 69) and the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People (UNDRIP). In Tamil Nadu, India, as another example, small-scale fishers have to compete for resources and space with expansionary large-scale fishing fleets. And, in the Amazon region, although the recognition that indigenous peoples' land rights are inalienable and permanent, the land was nevertheless used as collateral by the Peruvian Government.

Another problem is the reliance on values that tend to be interpreted as solely 'traditional.' This colonial viewpoint that consists of the Other or of the 'Noble Savage' where a timeless rural peasant or indigenous 'superhero' lives 'in nature' and is resistant to the temptations of capitalism or novel technologies, are brought to light and (Boldt 2017). The values embedded in the cultural philosophies have also been applied in a superficial manner to achieve a specific political interest, thereby diminishing the deep meaning of the concept, including the acknowledgement of Indigenous perspective and worldviews as part of reconciliation between the State and Indigenous people, but nevertheless permitting extractive and often unwanted projects in Indigenous territories where many frequently live in abysmal conditions (McGregor 2014). Rather than interpreting the philosophies of good life as a remedy to climate change or to the crisis of capitalism, it is important to draw on them as lenses testifying to humanity's cultural wealth and creative genius that can assist in addressing problems in social development and biodiversity degradation. As Jimenez and Roberts (2019) write, these epistemologies may inform innovation processes to produce different outcomes. Without essentializing, therefore, any proposed civilizational shift seeking to reverse the human separation from nonhuman nature must be critical and inclusive of all voices and perspectives and at arm's length from any neoliberal tendencies (Cochrane 2014; Espinosa 2017). Relying on the philosophies for acknowledgement of local and traditional governance, for pushing the limits of government discourse, and strengthening global to local advocacy and activism that recognizes territoriality has been fundamental for a number of indigenous and local communities. Justice and territorial rights means having the ability to choose, create, resist, reject, and change laws and policies that affect one's life and community, and inherent within the diverse philosophies of a good life, exists the notion that to pursue a good life, one must be free to live according to one's aspirations (Borrows Cadieux-Shaw, L 2017).

Finally, territories and rights are needed for the survival of IPCL: just like a scientist needs a lab to grow, create, and live out his/her aspirations, IPCLs need their cultural space to live out their lives.

In sum:

- **Territory as foundation for living out cultural philosophy.** A total of 19 articles discussed land as and fundamental space for living out the culture and the epistemologies within the cultural philosophies, including a coexistence between Nature and humans.
- **Rights are based and acted upon on land.** 91% of the articles emphasized that rights of IPCL are grounded in lands and resources and the promotion and protection of those rights, including legal recognition, are a continual struggle for IPLC.
- **Philosophies of good living can be used to empower communities.** Communities relying on their cultural philosophies found self-determination over their food systems (21 articles), resilience (4 articles), cultural revitalization (48 articles), and stronger governance of their natural resources (4 articles).

Topic 6: Capacity development (moving forward, looking for solutions)

“Capacity development is presented as one of the main levers that can lead to transformative change by tackling the underlying indirect drivers of nature deterioration (IPBES 2019). Capacity development can be described across six broad capacity dimensions. These dimensions are based on existing frameworks for adaptive capacity to climate change (Gupta et al., 2010) and risk management and vulnerability to natural hazards (Kuhlicke et al., 2011; Kuhlicke & Steinführer, 2015). The six dimensions that are explained in more detail below, embody many concepts and principles for capacity development and recognition in decision making.”

Motivational capacity: building awareness and desire to consider diverse values

Rationale: Related to KM 7 of “*how nature and biodiversity are conceptualized, which is directly linked with the way they are valued and with the decision-making processes related to their management*”.

The literature shows that there may be alternative motivations for including other set of values that could influence decision making. It challenges dominant understandings of concepts such as welfare, the common good and development (6, 307, 396). These set of values have a more intrinsic character rather than instrumental and provide special emphasis to social well-being for which values such as reciprocity and communality prevail to those focused on the individual. These set of values also include those intrinsic granted to nature, which also challenge the dominant expectations of development and economic life. In sum, the literature presents an alternative view to that of economic growth, encouraging decommodification, decentralization and redistribution of wealth and power (5). It represents a more idealistic as opposed to materialistic view of a subjective quality of life in support of sustainable policies and practices with positive attitudes towards ecological protection, redistribution of wealth and support for the welfare state (542). The Good-Life philosophy provides three core aspects that can contribute to motivational aspects for capacity development. Alternative views of what **economic life** can be that challenges the dominant development agenda and that embraces ideals mainly regarding human relations (focusing mostly on **reciprocity and communal life or communality**) and of human relationships with nature (framed mostly within a **biocentric perspective**). Examples of what these concepts are provided as follow:

Economic life. As an alternative view of economic life, examples include the notion of a "solidarity economy", based on a "love" ethic as a mutually reciprocal and relational core for social change (182; 318). Also, the idea that the economy could be based on many markets, all in service to society (4). It is implied that development or progress, as most people comprehend it, is avoidable, and these notions are important for putting forward incentives to protect nature and to promote respect for nature (308). Favor austerity over consumption and attention to social relationships over attention to making money; the concept of a "simple life" (74). The literature also challenges the dominant concept of 'sustainable development' when it perpetuates the idea of infinite growth and overreliance on markets for improved well-being. Rather, emphasis is made on social reciprocity and ecological equilibrium that can inspire others seeking to support local food sovereignty, ecological diversity and economies based on solidarity rather than greed (30).

Reciprocity/ communality. A "harmonious coexistence", based on values such as reciprocity among humans and with nature (198, 396). An inclusive paradigm that embraces "human beings living in

harmony with each other and the environment" (112). Respect for diversity and cultural identity, in a community coexistence, with interculturality and without power asymmetries. The latter implies that "you can't live well if others live badly" (6). According to 609, there are many proposals of communal life that integrate values that bring about the maintenance of good relations with others and one's surroundings. Reciprocity involves values such as: friendship, alliance, trust, humanity and community, respect, and coexistence (47).

Bio-centrism. Recognizing and assigning values based on a bio-centric perspective (2). Rejection of the human-nature divide whereby non-human entities such as plants, animals, and spirits, together with humans, form an extended community of local relationships (3). Non-human entities are considered subjects instead of objects in this extended community. Their rights and wellbeing are considered equally important to those of humans (334). This biocentric view is based on an alternative ethical perspective and understanding of the significance of unity within diversity, which supports a permanent pressure of reciprocity, complementarity, interconnection, and concordance among the various elements of life (396). It implies that all beings, although they are not identical, have an ontological value, even when they may not be of benefit to humans (609). It implies horizontal relationships with nature, nature beings as subjects with their own "agenda", implying an understanding of the world as unstable and plural (417). Urban contexts are presented as a challenge for this model (396).

Bridging (facilitation of dialogue and learning) and negotiating (enable collaborative relations and practices) different epistemologies (knowledge systems and set of values)

Rationale: Bridging capacity. Provides knowledge and tools to analyze multiple values. Brings together different ways of knowing and doing, often creating new knowledge in the process. **Negotiating capacity.** Enable collaborative relations and practices for navigating trade-offs regarding different epistemologies (knowledge systems and set of values) and mainstreaming into policy and practice. **Bridging and negotiation are needed to create enabling institutional contexts able to effectively address unequal power relations between stake and knowledge holders.** "The involvement of IPLCs in co-designing management plans can favor the confluence of different epistemologies in collaborative governance schemes, which can occur by complementing, confronting and/or contrasting different knowledge systems and plurality of values". (KM7). Also, negotiating is needed for incorporating ILK in decision-making processes to achieve better futures..."(KM 13), and promoting Intercultural dialogue and the construction of bridges between indigenous, local and scientific knowledge benefit natural resources management and other social-ecological practices (KM 14).

This literature emphasizes that to be able to create enabling institutional contexts, a decolonizing perspective needs to be approached by recognizing other ways of seeing and doing things. Also, that "local ways of knowing" (187) can bring alternative scenarios to progress. It addresses the importance of autonomy for innovation, but also the integration of values that are immerse in those ways of thinking (257). These values generally emphasize on the collective, with innovation benefiting the commons rather than individuals (for example, 257), or through favoring "popular economies" (30; 241). In Andean life, for example, the popular economy (although recently institutionalized into Constitutions; 598) emphasize social reciprocity and ecological equilibrium, aiming at local food sovereignty and favoring ecological diversity, local production, and subsistence farming (30; 41). Currently reflected in new agroecological paradigms (598). Another example of the importance of

local values and traditions is provided by Africa (although extended to the whole philosophy of Good-Living; 609) in terms of the relevance given to communal interactions in all aspects of life (583), and even as a peace mediating concept (417). In economic life, an example can be the concept of fair dealing, in which reciprocity is provided not only regarding the parties' own relationship, but also referring to the harmony of the greater community as a whole (241).

Bridging and negotiation is important because in many contexts, local values and traditions are undermined (534). As a response, this literature brings to our attention the importance of alternative epistemic communication (570). It also provides experiences of intercultural dialogues aimed at decolonizing knowledge through integrating a plurality of worldviews and placing importance on sensitivities, affections, and spirituality (334). It points towards the need of "Intergenerational connectedness" that implies important aspects of identity and that leads to a self- and value-laden awareness (569). In general terms, "Good living" philosophies represent "...a community-centric, ecologically-balanced and culturally-sensitive set of worldviews whose plural nature opens up the possibilities for bridging cultures and knowledge systems" (334), showing paths "...to proceed towards a broader and all-encompassing human coexistence with the natural and material environment" (47).

Analytical capacity: knowledge and tools to analyze multiple values

***Rationale:** Incorporating ILK in decision-making processes by promoting IPLCs self-research... ; (by) promoting the relation between the youth and the elders and leaders of IPLC; (by) involving Indigenous and Local voices in policymaking.. and ...translating indigenous worldviews/cosmovisions into adjusting official institutional norms (KM13). Intercultural dialogue and the construction of bridges between indigenous, local and scientific knowledge benefit natural resources management and other social-ecological practices. collaborative knowledge to build transformative capacities (KM 14).*

The literature exemplifies the importance of integrating local ways of knowing for deriving local solutions, as well as the importance of integrating concepts value-laden into analytical processes.

Specific examples are provided regarding new ways of doing research presented as alternatives to the dominant or traditional research paradigms. Indigenous research in Australia, for example, is illustrative of this point (593; 609). These works point to their value not only regarding methodologies and means (i.e., invoking indigenous knowledge and spirituality frameworks to dialogue with researchers; invoking concepts such as "deep listening"; participatory methodologies to select indicators of wellbeing) but also to the ends themselves (i.e., empowering women; restoring indigenous women's leadership and indigenous communities; indigenous as agents of their own development; 593). It is also brought out to the table the importance of self-determination for advancing in knowledge "Research paradigms and associated methodologies need to privilege Indigenous ways of knowing and ensure that Indigenous peoples, as collaborators and not as 'research subjects', fully and meaningfully participate" (609). There are other examples that demonstrate how indigenous science and integrating other ways of knowing can be critical for resolving specific issues (303). Also, of how autonomy and community-based research serves for revaluing concepts of progress and well-being (187).

Furthermore, the literature brings examples of ways for addressing children education as a leveler for change. For this, several proposals have been made, including those that adopt core aspects of distant

traditions (Ubuntu and Teko porã principles; 417) to promote child wellbeing in interconnection with collective wellbeing, which considers the “..environment, community, family, intergenerational and spiritual connectedness...” (417). There are other examples that focus on early stages of education for knowledge restoration and instilling a sense of interconnectedness of land with health and wellbeing (Connectedness Framework; 569). Further, “cultural authenticity” is important for African (higher) education to transform its colonial influences ().

Social network capacity: capacity to learn together, act and adapt or transform

Rationale: *Social network capacity KM.13 – celebrating agreements and partnerships achieved through networking between IPLCs’ groups.. (and) internationally, through capacity-building to form indigenous leaders, advocacy work and support from various stakeholders.*

This literature poses great emphasis on how the philosophies of Good living endorse human relations and reciprocity among humans and to nature (609). It is much at the core of these traditions. In terms of social networks, these tied interconnections translate into socially meaningful relationships (Prell, et al. 2007), providing cultural identity in close relationship with nature. Network capacity, however, can also be extended to outreach relations that provide good examples of learning together (local knowledge and research institutes). An illustrative example of the latter is based on the Satoumi concept which implies improving seascape productivity through management, and for that, learning together was found to be useful (373). Another example is the integrating of indigenous science for planning water management (303). Fisheries co-management activities as part of a multilevel coordinating body focusing on rights and licenses, local regulation of the use of commons, environmental management, and conservation (373). And other examples that integrate management and co-management for increasing livelihood conditions (wellbeing) through the integration of local values and knowledge and with a focus on wellbeing rather than wealth (258; 255). Another case regarding networks, provided by the literature, is the relevance of integrating more equal relations, for example, with reference to gender (6). Generally speaking, Buen vivir proposes complementary relationships with no exclusion, based on respect and coexistence “because nothing and nobody is useful by itself” (47).

Governance capacity: creating an enabling and socially just governance environment

Rationale: *Creating an enabling and socially just governance environment “Recognition and respect, at all scales, of the existing customary laws and processes” (KM13)*

Most of this literature vests on the importance of self-determination within capacity development for strengthening governance and, with it, well-being. For example, in the context of resistance to land dispossession (220). Or for self-managed development, in the context of social enterprise as a meaningful tool for the development of indigenous peoples in Latin America (179). It also presents the Buen vivir philosophy (or Buenos vivires in plural; 542), as based on tradition and ancestry ties, but also as “...new.. in the sense that they are now informing ethnopolitical projects” of different IPLC contexts. Particularly, “respect and support to the productive practices and management styles, to the knowledge systems and their expression within intercultural education systems; recognition and fulfilment of their rights as citizens, broader frames for participation, recognition of their customary rights, recognition of their local representatives election processes, recognition of their health

systems, establishment of community and regional autonomy guidelines, complete use and learning of ancestral languages and religions, and access to current intercommunication and information” (29). This philosophy, although coming from the local, feeds opposition to hegemonic systems and neoliberalism (542).

Topic 7: Formal and informal education

IPLCs' philosophies are part of urban and rural communities in different Latin American and African countries, also in the Philippines, Canada, Australia and Alaska (Table 1). The education under IPLCs' philosophies works is being done on community socio-environmental education, social inclusion and good living. Three basic principles that unite these works are [104, 214]: (a) dialogue of knowledge, (b) strategies anchored in the territorial area, (3) continuous training of promoters.

IPLCs' philosophies propose an intercultural conception of social inclusion [163, 104, 325, 593, 572, 583]. The work considers three stages: (i) recovery and reconstruction of knowledge of the different cultures related to Good Living (often with the support of scholarships for students from Native Peoples); (ii) transmission and promotion of the knowledge worked in the previous stage; and (iii) reciprocity turned to society by promoters of Good Living, arising from the previous stages, where the apprehended knowledge of giving-receiving-returning can be captured and reproduced.

With colonization and the paradigm of modernity, a model of education centered on the school as a learning space separated from daily and community life was imposed. Faced with this, critical decolonial, postcolonial and anti-hegemonic discourses emerge, which seek to put Euro-universalism in relative terms through dialogues and intercultural educational practices that reinvent non-colonial ways of life [163, 214, 277, 570, 600].

IPLCs' philosophies acknowledge diversity and demand genuine intercultural dialogues, and among the core principles of "buen vivir" education is: (a) intercultural cooperation, (b) reciprocity, and (c) collective action and solidarity [163, 200, 334, 357, 590]. Education reaches far beyond the school and is embedded in the community everyday life, including close relationships with nature [163, 200, 273, 334, 618, 74], guided by indigenous and peasants worldviews and practices [130, 334, 357, 417, 465, 478, 571, 572, 569].

IPLCs philosophies and buen vivir education foster Earth Stewardship (included in Chapter 5) by (i) balancing personal autonomy with community participation [163], (ii) acknowledging the key roles played by women and the pressures they experience [6, 593], (iii) teaching values for the preservation of culture and life [276, 277, 334, 569, 583, 590, 600], (iv) celebrating spirituality that connects humans and nature and heals historical trauma [569, 571], and (v) connecting different generations [417, 569]. Regarding the latter, children, youth and adults interact in different community spaces allowing the construction of the individual as a group [417]. Intergenerational education brought into the school environment ensures the well-being of children connected to their communities and the world [417, 569].

To implement these concepts and practices, formal modern schools will have to undertake intercultural dialogues enabling the participation of indigenous teachers as well as community members in decision making [35, 163]. These transformations are necessary to reconnect with nature not as something external to society and to advance social-environmental justice by integrating biocultural diversity into formal and non-formal education [163, 334].

Links with cross-cutting themes

Regarding **economy and development**, regarding economy and development, some papers relate it from social and solidarity economy (200, 273). The Sumak Kawsay economy promotes a diverse, healthy, sufficient production, to share, to trade and for self-consumption. Education is a tool to include those philosophies of Good Living in different development models (277, 334, 599, 571). However, making effective the incorporation of the economies of Good Living implies reviewing the concept of sustainability in indigenous knowledge and going beyond the dominant epistemologies (277). Other community development models are based on redistribution, emphasize leadership development, and affirm post-development premises (35, 258, 334, 86, 325).

Regarding **agriculture**, in relationship with the Good Living economies, the promotion of food sovereignty through food production is central. Agroecological farmer 'schools are relevant in these contexts, emerging as an option to integrate and apply certain technologies in specific contexts of rural life with their values. For this reason, community pedagogy, to be productive, must necessarily be linked to Mother Earth and the cycles of life (334, 571).

In the case of **gender**, education under gender perspective presents information on Indigenous and Aboriginal women's movements for ensuring their rights, recognizing the current sufferings that stem from colonialism (6, 593). They are articulated to the gender, the **storytelling** as a vehicle that transmits values between generations of women and connects feminine power with the earth embodied in Mother Earth (582, 593).

Regarding **protected areas**, one paper recounts how conservation policies along with other international policies have increased pressure for the Maasai land in Africa. The Tarangire National Park impacts people in Simanjiro due to the lack of inclusion of local values and ways of life in decision-making (599).

Another relevant issue was **public policies**, in the Plurinational State of Bolivia, the fundamental principles of good living are recognized in the National Education Policy. The biocentric conception is assumed as an inclusive and comprehensive public policy that promotes socio-community values throughout the pedagogical process (59, 570). In Brazil, indigenous people seek to enter through intercultural dialogues in the political, judicial, legislative, cultural and social system of the state, trying to live and maintain their identity as indigenous people, challenging a monocultural school model (163).

Table 1. Main themes that emerge from the analysis of the codified works for the education topic and their distribution among countries of the different continental regions. European region is excluded from the table because no studies were found on the topic.

Main themes emerging	Americas	Asia Pacific	Africa	Oceania
Decoloniality, power (asimmetrical) relations, teorías críticas postcoloniales	Bolivia (6, 59); Ecuador, Argentina, Mexico (86); Colombia (334), Brazil (163), Latin America in general (570, 590)	non-specific (600)	South Africa (214, 277); Malawi (277); Tanzania (599); Rwanda and others countries (552); non-specific (583, 600)	Australia (593)
Community empowerment through participation in educational process, "liberation teology", formal and practical education based on-experiential	Brazil (128); Colombia (334); Mexico (571)		South Africa (258)	
Formal "conventional" education, in complement with OR in contrast to, community-based knowledge	Canada (303)		Kenya, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Nigeria, Senegal, Ethiopia, Zambia and Malawi (276); Zambia (534); Tanzania (599)	
Intercultural Education (High-level and other levels, formal and practical), Indigenous knowledge	Ecuador (62, 273); Mexico (166); Brazil (538); Latin America in general (590)		Kenya, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Nigeria, Senegal, Ethiopia, Zambia and Malawi (276); Malawi and South Africa (277)	Australia (593)
Teachers and professional training in intercultural and informal education model (some relation education with biocultural heritage and tourism)	Ecuador (104, 325)		South Africa and Sahara (572); non-specific (583)	Australia (593)
Informal education through oral narratives, metaphors and stories (ecoliteracy?)	Canada (582)		Zambia (534)	
Community pedagogy (ways of educating) based on life cycles, in buenos vivires, teaching-learning in community - aboriginal / indigenous pedagogy based on indigenous perspective, indigenous ethic or epistemology	Bolivia (35, 59); Mexico (130, 361); Brazil (163, 417); Ecuador (200, 273); Canada (303, 478); Colombia (334, 579); Peru (618); Alaska (569)	Philipines (74)	South Africa (465, 572); Sahara (572)	
Chilhood, "childification", intergenerational connectedness	Brazil (417); Alaska (569)			

Power issues in the good living philosophies

From the 204 coded papers regarding the good living philosophies from IPLC, a total of 140 papers or 69% address power issues whether implicitly or explicitly. These papers evince the different spheres in which power operates (Annex 2.1) usually creating contentious spaces between IPLC and other actors (e.g. political actors, elites, private actors, among others) [513; 598; 576; 83; 129; 513; 24; 309; 240; 241; 408; 216]. Very often, these tensions are the product of different values of Nature and who is able to make decisions and enforce them regarding those values.

Even though some aspects of these philosophies have been incorporated into policy and efforts to pursue sustainability aligned values by political agendas have been made [573; 171; 149; 363; 46; 219; 202; 37; 439; 578; 443; 573; 126; 197]¹, prevalence of pre-existing forms of extractivism and accumulation of Nature and Nature depelation behind this incorporation remain. These contradictions to implement notions of these philosophies at national and international levels [46; 111; 513], points to the structural power and the complexity of incorporating other Nature values into laws embedded in the broader capitalist economic system.

As for many philosophies of good living around the world whose inclusion or institutionalization of their values and principles are in early stages or currently being negotiated, the case of the Buen Vivir philosophy, and its inclusion in the constitutions of Ecuador and Bolivia, offers an interesting case to analyze. Although great progress has been recognized by scholars and practitioners regarding how the Buen Vivir discourse has permeated the political realm, new challenges have emerged as this discourse has been pointed out to be taken rhetorically in some cases. The issues of how the same constitution promotes economic development favouring extractivist activities like mining or oil extraction, and on the other side recognizes Nature as a legal subject with different rights, exposes the inherent structural/legal contradictions or dilemmas [307, 126, 149], above all when these two issues converge in the same territory.

One of the most relevant examples is the Yasuni-ITT Initiative, in the Ecuadorian Amazon which shows the immaturity of international ecological policies [72, 82, 126, 306, 307, 570]. This experience was characterized by the lack of economic support from the international community to keep oil underground in the Yasuni territory, an area characterized by its rich biodiversity, the presence of different Indigenous groups, and unexploited oil richness. Yasuni-ITT initiative refers to Ishpingo-Tambococha- Tiputini, three untapped oil blocks. This initiative was part of the agenda of the Long-Term Cooperative Action under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Through a trust fund co-managed by the Ecuadorian government and the UNDP, the idea was that the international community will contribute 50 % of the income that would have been generated from oil exploitation, in order to protect biodiversity and keep social programs. After a period of time only 0.37 % of the estimated income was achieved and in 2013, the government of Ecuador finalized the Yasuni-ITT initiative and started oil drilling in part of the territory. This generated the mobilization of different

¹ Examples of these inclusion into policy agendas are: Bhutan gross national happiness, Rights of Nature or "Pachamama" in the constitutions of Ecuador and Bolivia, the "Planes de Vida" in Colombia, the Yasuni ITT Initiative or Ubuntu in different countries of Africa.

IPLCs, activists and other sympathizers to reject the decision of the government, yet opinions were divided regarding this final decision.

Although it is recognized that “the Yasuní-ITT initiative, together with the rights of nature in the Constitution is undoubtedly the most important and symbolical contribution of Ecuador on a global level” (Lalander, 2014: 163 [307]), this initiative also shows the difficulty to achieve the goals and embedded values in this philosophies of good living in practice. Especially evident is the discursive power carried by global political agendas that promote mainly economic development and subrogate environmental protection.